

Impact of Celebrity Endorsement and peer influence on Impulsive buying Behaviour: mediating and moderating role of Impulsiveness and social media use

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ABSTRACT: The motivation for this research is to investigate the factors that shape the personality trait impulsiveness of young adults and, then, the outcomes of impulsiveness. impulsiveness is used as a mediator between contextual factors (celebrity endorsement and peer influence) and impulsive buying. Further, social media is used as moderating variable in the fast-food sector of Pakistan. The Data was collected from the undergraduate university students residing in the Punjab province of Pakistan. Structural Equation Modeling Technique was used to analyse the data. The results of the study show that the impulsiveness of young adults is more involved in impulsive buying. The results also confirm the findings of previous researches conducted in other cultures. It also confirms that Impulsiveness mediates the relationship between sociological factor (celebrity endorsement and peer influence) and impulsive buying behaviour. Moreover, it proves the moderating role of the social media use in determining and affecting these relationships. This research provides guidelines for the researchers, policy makers, and managers.

Keywords: Celebrity Endorsement, Peer Influence, Impulsiveness, Social Media Use, Impulsive Buying

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1. Introduction

Considerable attention has been devoted by scholars in the field of marketing psychology towards the phenomenon of obsessive buying behaviour (K. Chan et al., 2006; Inglehart & Baker, 2000). The diverse array of wants, needs, and aspirations exhibited by individuals results in a broad spectrum of purchasing patterns among customers. The purchasing habits of individuals are influenced by a variety of factors, including but not limited to their social, cultural, psychological, and environmental components. The process of shopping is subject to several internal and external forces, both direct and indirect, which significantly impact key decision-making. In order to complete a purchase, an individual is required to engage in a series of decision-making processes. Compulsive buying behaviour can be characterized as the impulsive and compulsive acquisition of superfluous items. In the year 2003, a collective sum of \$175 billion was expended by 32 million individuals aged 12 to 19 in the United States (Mangleburg et al., 2004), the current generation possesses a significantly greater quantity of toys compared to teenagers from two to three decades ago, with a fourfold increase. Adolescents between the ages of 16 and 18 residing in the United Kingdom had a notable inclination towards compulsive shopping, acknowledging the challenges associated with refraining from purchasing unnecessary items (Phau & Woo, 2008). Prior studies have examined and enhanced our comprehension of the main antecedents of impulsive buying behaviour (Jalees, 2009). Impulsive purchasing can be characterized as a compelling and uncontrolled desire to immediately acquire things and services, sometimes with limited contemplation of the potential consequences associated with the purchase (Aragoncillo & Orus, 2018). Due to the propensity of individuals to engage in impulsive behaviour, there are instances where consumer purchasing patterns undergo unforeseen transformations, often driven by spontaneous urges. The presence of urges has been identified as a noteworthy factor in human motivation, capable of exerting influence over individuals' behaviours in particular ways. Moreover, the main impulses experienced by individuals are predominantly rooted in physiological needs, whereas secondary wants are significantly shaped by societal factors and external influences. These influences may manifest in the form of acquiring desired commodities or possessions that are perceived as symbols of social standing within a certain cultural context (Kang & Park-Poaps, 2010). To a certain degree, the manifestation of socially harmful behaviours might be observed under certain conditions. Moreover, primary physiological urges hold paramount importance in human beings, while secondary urges exert a substantial influence on our behaviour and are influenced by social factors and pressures. These may include the acquisition of desired goods or those that are deemed to confer social status within a given society, such as purchasing items that are considered prestigious in a particular social context (Kang & Park-Poaps, 2010). Drawing upon these foundational elements, individuals deliberately cultivate novel desires, such as a propensity for fast food consumption or engagement in substance misuse, so precipitating the emergence of addictive behaviours. An analogous perspective was put out by (Workman, 2010), The individual in question perceived consumer purchasing behaviour as a matter of concern, highlighting its deviant nature that negatively impacts several aspects of an individual's life, including interpersonal connections and occupational challenges. Peer-to-peer interaction, often known as P2P interaction, refers to the exchange of information, ideas, and experiences between individuals who are at a similar level of knowledge (Moschis & Churchill Jr, 1978), Peer consumer socialization refers to the explicit interactions that occur between a young individual and their peers in the context of acquiring and consuming goods. Research indicates that peer influence has a crucial role, especially in situations when alcohol consumption is readily apparent (Saunders et al., 1973). The development of a new identity and the cultivation of self-reliance are crucial aspects of adolescence. Individuals acquire the ability to autonomously make increasingly complex decisions.

Adolescents exhibit a greater inclination to actively pursue interpersonal connections that demonstrate an understanding of their viewpoints and validate their emotions. Peer groups, due to the common experiences they possess, are an inevitable and inherent means of establishing connections. Consequently, children have a heightened sense of camaraderie and inclusion among their peer group. Due to ongoing engagement with peers, they can assume the role as the predominant source of social comparison, surpassing even parental figures in frequency. There is a growing global trend of celebrity endorsement and idolization, wherein young individuals are progressively expressing admiration and emulating celebrities, including their possessions and the items they support. In recent times, there has been a growing prevalence of a particular behaviour among civilizations predominantly composed of young individuals (Grewal et al., 2018). According to a recent study, there is a growing trend of employing celebrities to endorse and market products targeted towards the younger demographic. Consequently, this phenomenon has led to an increased inclination among young individuals towards materialism (Pradhan et al., 2018). Moreover, superstars garner the attention of young individuals due to their perceived credibility as purveyors of information, hence enhancing their popularity among the younger demographic. Certain individuals engage in the acquisition of products with the primary objective of augmenting their social distinctiveness or elevating their perceived social status, whereas others procure commodities for alternative motivations (Jin & Ryu, 2019). Numerous investigations pertaining to impulsive buying behaviour have been undertaken within Western nations, but very limited scholarly attention has been directed towards third-world countries such as Pakistan. (Jalees, 2009). Research indicates that the phenomenon of economic expansion has a positive correlation with the propensity of consumers to engage in impulsive buying behaviour (Kacen & Lee, 2002). Pakistan's gross domestic product (GDP) has demonstrated a sustained growth trajectory, surpassed the 5% mark and attained a notable 5.79% in the fiscal year 2018. This achievement is the best level of economic performance witnessed in the past 13 years, signifying a positive upturn in the country's overall economic landscape (Hafeez & Fasih, 2018; Pakistan Economic Survey 2018). The significance of examining impulsive purchasing behaviour in Pakistan has been heightened in light of recent developments. The primary purpose of this research is to analyze how endorsement from famous people and social pressure play into spontaneous purchases. This study also intends to investigate the moderating effect of social media use and the mediating function of impulsivity.

2. Literature Review

Peer influences

The extent to which one's peers can affect one's thoughts, feelings, and actions is a typical definition of peer influence (Bristol & Mangleburg, 2005). Numerous conceptualizations have been put out, albeit with varying perspectives (Makgosa & Mohube, 2007). Numerous theoretical perspectives claim that active participation in social interactions with peers plays a pivotal role in promoting both cognitive development and the acquisition of social skills (Mowen & Spears, 1999). Peers play a significant role in the lives of children, exerting influence over their purchasing decisions as they engage in increased social interactions (Kongsholm, 2007). According to (Xie & Singh, 2007), The impact of friends on consumer behaviour is significantly more pronounced than that of parents. Research has indicated that the impact and sway exerted by peer groups on the younger generation surpasses that of parental pressure and influence. According to the complete social assessment theory, individuals engage in self-evaluation by either comparing their financial assets to those of their peers or by assessing their social standing (Islam et al., 2018).

Peer Influence and Impulsiveness

Additionally, research has demonstrated that impulsive buying behaviour can be influenced by peer communication (Bapna & Umyarov, 2015). Moreover, as per a researcher specializing in consumer psychology, psychological variances, which constitute a significant facet of an individual's personality, exert a considerable influence on impulsive buying behaviour (Zafar et al., 2019). The theory of social comparison posits that consumers engage in a process of evaluating their personal possessions in relation to those of prominent individuals, with the aim of ascertaining their social standing (Motl et al., 2001). The objective of the trait activation theory (TAT) is to provide an explanation for the interaction between individual qualities and situational factors. The present hypothesis suggests that the manifestation of a trait is influenced by the arousal elicited by environmental cues that are relevant to that trait. Organizational behaviour study frequently utilizes this theory to elucidate the correlation between personality traits and the surrounding environment in order to forecast behavioural consequences (Anseel et al., 2007; Kamdar & Van Dyne, 2007; Tett & Guterman, 2000). We hypothesized:

H1: Peer Influence has a significant influence on Impulsiveness

Celebrity Endorsement

The concept of celebrity endorsement is characterized by (McCracken, 1989b) as: "An individual who possesses a notable public presence and utilizes this recognition to promote a consumer product through their appearance in a commercial is commonly referred to as a "celebrity". According to (Boorstin, 1961), A celebrity can be defined as a someone who has achieved a significant level of recognition and popularity, typically stemming from their involvement in many domains such as athletics, politics, entertainment, medicine, or their association with other notable figures within the celebrity sphere (Yue & Cheung, 2000). This, according to (Weir et al., 1991), This may be attributed to individuals possessing a profound desire for interpersonal connection and a sense of self-identification. Moreover, the phenomenon of celebrity worship can exert a substantial influence on the attitudes, behaviours, and values of individuals who engage in such admiration (Arratia & Schultze, 1991). Adolescents and young consumers everywhere exhibit a strong fascination with the adoration of public people (Yue & Cheung, 2000b), and The phenomenon of idolizing celebrities is pervasive within global youth cultures. Based on a recent estimation, it has been observed that prominent figures are employed as brand ambassadors in approximately 20% of global advertisements. the research conducted, it may be concluded that (Shimp & Andrews, 2013)

H2: Celebrity Endorsement has a significant influence on Impulsiveness

Impulsiveness

Costa and McCrae (1992) assert in their NEO Personality Inventory-Revised model that impulsiveness is a defining trait associated with neuroticism. The aforementioned characteristic, encompassing traits such as adverse impact, susceptibility to stress, lack of impulse control, and postponement of gratification, may manifest as a propensity for impulse buying. Internet-based technology (IBT) is distinguished by the presence of a significant and potentially detrimental element, namely a lack of control. Individuals with neurotic tendencies exhibit a proclivity towards pursuing rapid fulfillment in order to fulfill their desires (Youn & Faber, 2000). Individuals may experience a sense of deprivation if they refrain from acquiring even an item that fails to fulfill their respective desires. The proposition posits that humans exhibit spontaneous behaviour. The inclination to make impulsive purchases can be categorized as a consumer attribute referred to as impulsiveness, which is reinforced by the inherent human characteristic of impulsivity. The shopping lists of individuals who engage in impulsive buying behaviour exhibit a higher degree of receptiveness and flexibility towards unplanned purchases compared to the lists

of individuals who adopt a more systematic shopping approach. Moreover, their cognitive processes are prone to lacking critical analysis, as they are primarily guided by the spatial closeness to a wanted object, influenced by an emotional affinity towards it, and captivated by the allure of instant gratification (Hoch & Loewenstein, 1991; Thompson et al., 1990).

Impulsive Buying Behaviour

Impulsive purchasing behaviours present a plethora of research prospects for marketing researchers with an interest in consumer behaviour. Additionally, marketing managers must consider these behaviours due to their potential to yield substantial profits for a company (Z. Liu et al., 2019). There are various elements that can serve as triggers for impulsive buying behaviour. Numerous consumer transactions are driven by psychological motivations, including the intrinsic need for a sense of accomplishment or uniqueness, alongside the aspiration to enhance one's self-worth. Additional purchases may be influenced by social reasons, such as the aspiration to enhance one's perceived social status or obtain social approval. Impulse buying is widely recognized as a phenomenon of concern, often associated with factors such as low self-esteem, immaturity, financial challenges, product dissatisfaction, post-purchase dissatisfaction, and emotions of guilt or shame (Rook & Fisher, 1995), and an absence of regulation on an individual's conduct (Chen- Yu & Seock, 2002) The consequence of this is a negative perception by the general population (Rook, 1987). Impulse buying can be characterized as the convergence of internal elements, such as psychological and personality traits, and external factors, including social, environmental, and situational influences, among others (Vonkeman et al., 2017). The significance of impulsive buying in consumer behaviour has been evident for a number of years. According to scholarly and professional studies, impulsive purchases constitute a significant proportion, ranging from 40 to 80 percent, of all purchases, with the exact percentage varying according on the nature of the things being considered (Podoshen & Andrzejewski, 2012). The underlying psychological factors contributing to impulse purchase, along with the phenomenon of "impulse temptations," Researchers and corporations have made efforts to comprehend the psychological underpinnings of consumer behaviour with the aim of enhancing sales (Kacen et al., 2012a; Kacen & Lee, 2002).

Impulsiveness and Impulse Buying

According to (Dholakia, 2000), Customers who experience impulsive cravings during the purchasing process encounter difficulties in exerting control over their impulses. Consequently, a proposal is being put up regarding a positive correlation between the inclination to engage in impulsive purchasing and impulsive buying behaviour. Despite the limited body of research pertaining to customers' purchasing impulses, it is not unexpected that this phenomenon significantly influences consumers' impulsive purchase tendencies. Primarily, the inclination to make a purchase is influenced solely by positive emotions, rather than negative emotions (Flight et al., 2012). Moreover, individuals are increasingly prone to engaging in impulsive buying behaviour when their sense of urgency over purchasing intensifies (Beatty & Ferrell, 1998). In alternative terms, when customers have a sense of compulsion, they encounter challenges in resisting the physical appeal of the products (Hoch & Loewenstein, 1991) Ultimately, this lack of self-control hinders individuals from making rational choices, leading to impulsive behaviour (Han et al., 2009). In relation to the phenomenon of impulse buying, persons who exhibit a pronounced inclination are more susceptible to the persuasive impact of advertisements, thus engaging in the activity of perusing merchandise within physical retail establishments. Impulse buying is commonly linked to a personality feature referred to as "loss of control," wherein individuals who engage in impulsive purchasing exhibit limited cognitive capacity to resist making spontaneous purchases (Dawson & Kim, 2009; Youn & Faber, 2000).

H3: Impulsiveness has a significant impact on impulsive buying behaviour

Impulsiveness as Mediator

Mediating Role of Impulsiveness

The literature extensively documents an individual's inclination towards impulsive purchases, which has been demonstrated to significantly influence their decision-making process in terms of purchasing (Sanchez-Roige et al., 2019; Xiao & Nicholson, 2013). The propensity for individuals to engage in impulse buying is influenced by three key factors: socio-demographic, situational, and dispositional. In the initial stage, it is evident that socio-demographic variables, namely age and gender, exhibit a significant correlation with impulsive buying behaviour. Research suggests that there is a higher propensity for men to engage in impulsive purchases compared to women, and men tend to be older on average in comparison to women (BOZACI, 2020). In the context of influencing clients during the point of sale (POS), situational factors encompass a range of variables, including external and internal stimuli (such as marketing efforts), social dynamics (such as the presence of others), and various constraints (such as financial or time-related limitations). The marketing qualities of companies have a direct impact on the impulsive purchasing decisions made by consumers (Amos et al., 2014; Kacen et al., 2012b). In contrast, dispositional factors refer to individual variations in psychological qualities and dispositions. In a recent study conducted by (Chung & Cho, 2017), For instance, it has been shown that impulsive buying habits exert a substantial influence on the occurrence of impulse purchases in the context of online shopping. The decision-making style of individuals is regularly influenced by their dispositional features (Peck & Childers, 2006).

Many researchers have found that impulse buying is related to other types of impulsive behavior (Y.-H. Wang et al., 2016; X. Zhang et al., 2018). Traditional brick-and-mortar retail (Saad & Metawie, 2015) Impulsivity is strongly correlated with impulse buying. The histology data from an internet shopping study shows that impulsive purchases can increase hedonic value. Researchers (Gangai & Agrawal, 2016) found that impulsive buying significantly impacts purchase behavior. Impulsive people make more online impulse purchases, according to Zhang and colleagues (2018). In the context of online shopping, (Turkyilmaz et al., 2015) analyzed the impact of impulsiveness and other personality factors on the responses to signals presented on websites. The following hypothesis is proposed by us.

H4: Impulsiveness mediates the relationship between celebrity endorsement and impulsive buying behaviour

H5: Impulsiveness mediates the relationship between Peer Influence and impulsive buying behaviour

Social Media use

As it turns out, (Rabia et al., 2020), Individuals engage in the establishment of virtual communities and networks as a means of generating, disseminating, and interchanging information and ideas. Social media serves as a platform via which individuals engage in interpersonal communication and connect with others (Whiting & Williams, 2013). Alison Doyle, an American psychologist, As per her conceptualization of social media, individuals employ this platform to disseminate many forms of multimedia communication, including but not limited to text, audio, video, photos, and podcasts. Social media, as delineated by social media network platforms, refers to a virtual environment wherein individuals engage in communication pertaining to self-selected and self-generated information, entertainment, and news (Carah, 2017).According to (Mangold & Faulds, 2009), Social networking has become an inescapable phenomenon for the overwhelming majority of companies globally. There are several distinguishing factors that set social media use apart from traditional media use. These include the element of interactivity, the level of media richness, the presence of communities including individuals with shared ideals, and the capacity to exchange diverse visual content (Perloff, 2014). Online

applications like Facebook, Twitter, and many others make it easy for users to create and share original material (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010).

Social Media as Moderator

Social media has emerged as a prominent advertising medium that has exerted a substantial influence on the younger demographic. Both the younger generation and adults perceive social media as the most versatile and suitable platform for advertising in contemporary times, as opposed to television or other media formats. According to the State of Digital Advertising 2018 research by Adobe Digital Insights (ADI), there exists a notable disparity between younger age groups and older age groups in terms of their preferred channels. While the former predominantly identifies television as their most pertinent medium, the latter holds a contrasting viewpoint. The popularity of social media is on the rise due to the rising availability of youthful influencers for purchase through internet marketing. The influence of social media has extended beyond its original purpose of advertising. Based on a poll conducted in the previous year, it was found that the younger demographic tends to place greater trust in suggestions disseminated through social media platforms compared to those conveyed by television commercials. Moreover, new empirical evidence suggests that dialogues on social media platforms contribute to approximately 12% of consumer transactions in the Indian context. While older individuals continue to rely on television and traditional banner commercials, teens are increasingly engaging with various social media platforms, where they are consistently exposed to a multitude of advertisements. Commercials play a crucial role in influencing children's purchasing decisions, as materialism serves as a main factor in cultivating their urge to consume. The influence of social media on the development of a materialistic worldview among young individuals is noteworthy. Prominent social media networks employ a method to enhance the visibility and expedite the popularity of specific posts. These measures have a substantial role in assessing the value of oneself and others. It is expected that a substantial number of likes will be received. If you're using a social media site like Facebook, Instagram, or Twitter to spread your message, irrespective of whether the post pertains to conveying a societal message or capturing a self-portrait. This observation illustrates that individuals tend to assess their own value based on the actions of others and their respective inclinations or aversions. There is a growing tendency to assign comparable significance to online relationships as well as face-to-face contacts, as seen by the utilization of metrics like as Retweets or likes to assess one's personal value. Consequently, an increase in the quantity of what we receive corresponds to a corresponding elevation in our self-esteem, as it allows us to perceive ourselves as being socially esteemed.

H6: Social Media Use Moderates the relationship between celebrity endorsement and impulsiveness

H7: Social Media Use Moderates the relationship between Peer Influence and impulsiveness

SOR framework

The SOR model has garnered significant adoption and utilization within the realm of consumer behaviour research (Islam et al. 2018; Liu and Cao 2016). Based on the SOR model, the environment comprises different stimuli (S) that, when integrated, influence individuals' internal states and prompt them to behave as organisms (O), subsequently leading to the manifestation of behavioural reactions (R). The model has garnered empirical validation from a substantial corpus of scholarly literature (Vieira, Santini, and Araujo 2018). The proposition of this concept was initially formulated within the context of a retail setting. In this paradigm, the environmental stimulus consists of climatic cues, whereas the two primary emotional states are Organism and engaging in purchasing activities at the store as reactions. The consumer's internal states are significantly influenced by environmental stimuli. The application of the SOR model suggests that consumers' interior states are also

influenced by all external stimuli. In the framework developed by (Zheng et al. 2019) Stimuli such as ambient, design, and social cues are present. In this work, the researchers employed the SOR model to elucidate the connections among external stimuli, the internal state of the organism, and the resultant specific consequences. The present study employed the Stimulus-Organism-Response (SOR) model as the framework for examining the environmental stimulus. The social stimuli (S) in this study encompassed social influence, namely celebrity impact and peer influence, as well as social media use. The concept of materialism within the context of the organism (O). The remarks (R) made reference to the phenomenon of compulsive shopping, characterized by impulsive purchasing behaviour.

Hypothesis

H1: Peer Influence has a significant influence on Impulsiveness

H2: Celebrity Endorsement has a significant influence on Impulsiveness

H3: Impulsiveness has a significant impact on impulsive buying behaviour

H4: Impulsiveness mediates the relationship between celebrity endorsement and impulsive buying behaviour

H5: Impulsiveness mediates the relationship between Peer Influence and impulsive buying behaviour

H6: social media use moderates the relationship between celebrity endorsement and Impulsiveness

H7: social media use moderates the relationship between peer influence and impulsiveness

3. Methodology

When it comes to young Pakistani customers, there is little in the existing body of consumer behaviour and marketing literature that provides empirical data on the link between the predecessors of materialism and compulsive buying behaviour. The following conceptual model was developed for this study based on the existing body of literature. Several major insights have arisen in the context of young adults. The first thing to know is that impulsiveness is a strong indicator of impulse purchases. The second point is that impulsiveness is a powerful mediator between environmental influences and spontaneous

purchases. Thirdly, both peer influence and celebrity endorsement have been found to be significant predictors of impulsive behaviour. Finally, research shows that social media acts as a buffer between impulsiveness and the effect of celebrities and peers.

Measurement development

The questionnaire used in this analysis has its roots in previous academic research. Four items created by Wells et al. (2011) were employed in order to evaluate impulsivity. four from Items (Sheldon et al. 2004), Evaluation of celebrity endorsement was carried by using the Celebrity Endorsement Survey. Peer pressure was measured using three factors taken from (Mangleburg and Bristol 1998). To assess consumers' impulsive buying behaviour four item were used from (Ridgway et al. 2008). Social media use was measured by using 10 items from (DeVellis et al., 2003). Consequently, all components of the questionnaire were obtained from prior research. The parameters selected and incorporated into our conceptual model are among those that have been associated with impulsivity and impulsive buying behaviour in young individuals. Data collection was conducted using a quantitative approach. The assessment of all issues was conducted with a five-point Likert scale, which encompassed responses ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree." The absence of content validity concerns in Pakistan's colleges can be attributed to the predominant use of English as the primary language of instruction, as all educational materials and resources are developed in English (Islam et al., 2018; Rasool et al., 2012).

Data collection

Undergraduates were the target audience for this data presentation. There were 450 total respondents to the study; 227 were male and 223 were female. To ensure that the data is accurate, a survey was conducted. In quantitative research, surveys play a crucial role because they allow researchers to test hypotheses about relationships between variables. As a result, surveys are frequently used in the scientific research of social scientists (H. Zhang et al., 2014). Data was collected from undergraduate students at universities (major campuses) in Pakistan's Punjab region. Since college students tend to have more free time and money, they make for ideal participants in our study (K. Chan et al., 2006; Chou, 2001; Pinto et al., 2000). During the class, students were provided with a well-constructed questionnaire to be completed under the supervision of their lecturers. The researchers gave the students a brief overview of the many facets of the investigation before distributing the questionnaire. Of the original 450 replies, 17 were deemed insufficient for analysis due to missing information. As a result, 433 students' worth of information made up the final sample. There were roughly as many males as females among the respondents (50.44%). The ages of the people in question ranged from 18 to 30. Distributions of respondent characteristics are shown in Table 2.

Variable	Group	Frequencies	Percentages
Age	19 to 24 Years	383	85.1
	25 to 30 Years	67	14.9
Gender	Male	227	50.4
	Female	223	49.6
Part Time Job	Yes	86	19.1
	No	364	80.9
Per Month Spending in Fast Food	Less than Rs.1000	177	39.3
	Rs.1001 to 2000	104	23.1
	Rs. 2001 to 3000	75	16.7
	Above Rs.4000	94	20.9

Data analysis

Both structural equation modeling (SEM) and a partial least squares (PLS) method were used to examine the data. The reliability and validity of the proposed constructs were confirmed, and the measurement model was validated, thanks to this. When it comes to regression analysis, the Partial Least Squares (PLS) method is a tried-and-true option. Simultaneously, the variables A and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA).

Measurement model

In this investigation, CFA was used to assess the measurement model (Hair et al., 2012). The evaluation process commenced with an assessment of the measuring model's validity, specifically examining its substance, convergence, and discernment. Construct validity is widely recognized as one of the most challenging techniques in research (Malhotra, 2010). However, it is necessary for the purposes of this study, as it allows for any variations in the understanding of the concept and potential fluctuations in respondents' perceptions of the construct to be accounted for during the data collection process (Drost, 2011). Consequently, researchers place more emphasis on the data gathering phase. A preliminary pilot test was done, consisting of 50 questionnaire responses. Before to the primary data collection, verify the content's validity by checking its reliability, validity, and average variance extracted (AVE). During the course of our study, several items were removed, boosting the convergent and discriminant validities and increasing the alpha values as a result. The term "convergent validity" is used to describe the degree to which one construct is linked to other constructions within the same conceptual framework. Measures such as the average variance explained (AVE), Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability (CR), and factor loadings were used to determine convergent validity. In the realm of statistics, Cronbach's alpha is the gold standard for determining which structures can be trusted (Gefen & Straub, 2000). The concept of "internal consistency" of a latent variable pertains to the degree of consistency observed among its constituent elements. The concept of construct dependability refers to the absence of random error in the elements of a construct and the consistency of the obtained results. Ratings of reliability above 0.70 are considered satisfactory (Keil et al., 2000). All of the constructs tested in this research have Cronbach's alpha values over 0.70, as indicated in Table 2.

Discriminant validity pertains to the distinctiveness of each notion within the conceptual model. The assessment of discriminant validity was conducted (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). We looked at discriminant validity from a theoretical perspective. The correlation between variables was compared to the square root of the average of variables. The study's results suggest that the discriminant validity is adequate. Researchers have advised the use of Average Variance Extracted (AVE), Composite Reliability 0.50 for CR, 0.80 for Cronbach's alpha, and 0.70 for overall agreement (Faqih, 2016; Flynn et al., 1990). Table 2 shows that all of the measurement models' needed values are above the minimum level. As a result, the findings suggest strong discriminant and convergent validity.

Structural model assessment

Table 2: Construct wise Reliability Analysis

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Items	CR	AVE
Impulsiveness	0.859	4	0.868	0.622
Celebrity Endorsement	0.848	4	0.853	0.595
Peer Influence	0.887	4	0.898	0.688
Impulsive Buying Behaviour	0.891	4	0.885	0.658
Social Meida Use	0.905	10	0.915	0.546

The statistical evaluations of the model's validity and robustness led to the conclusion that it was fit for use in hypothesis testing. A direct association between the variables was initially determined using a correlation analysis. The term "correlation" refers to the link between two or more independent factors. Celebrity endorsement ($r = .403$, $p = 0.001$), peer influence ($r = .364$, $p = 0.001$), and the use of social media ($r = .373$, $p = 0.001$) were all found to have a positive link with impulsivity. There was a significant correlation between impulsiveness and impulse buying in young people ($r = 0.268$, $r = 0.350$, $P = 0.001$). Table 5 displays the results of the correlation analysis (see Fig. 1). Second, we tested our hypotheses by using Amos to run the structural equation model. Using the SEM method, the effect of the independent variables on the dependent variables was studied. Data analysis of the conceptual model shows that the antecedents' variables (celebrity endorsements, peer influence, and social media use) have a substantial effect on the dependent variables (impulsiveness and impulsive buying behavior). There are strong correlations between Impulsiveness and the following path coefficients: celebrity endorsement ($\beta = 0.309^{***}$, $p = 0.01$), peer influence ($\beta = 0.252^{***}$, $p = 0.01$), and social media use ($\beta = 0.224^{***}$, $p = 0.01$). As a result, hypotheses 1 and 2 are correct. Young people's obsessive buying behavior and materialism account for 24.7% of the variance in compulsive buying, and impulsiveness substantially predicted ($\beta = 0.081^{***}$, $p = 0.01$) impulsive buying behavior. Using parameter coefficients, it was determined that materialism is a major factor in both impulsive and compulsive buying behaviors. Path Coefficient and R2 Analysis of a Regression Model values is presented in Fig. 2.

Mediation analysis

Materialism acted as a go-between in the current study between (celebrity endorsing, peer influence, and impulse buying). Several psychologists and social scientists have debated mediation's efficacy (Baron & Kenny, 1986; Hayes & Scharkow, 2013; MacKinnon et al., 2002; Preacher & Hayes, 2004; Shrout & Bolger, 2002). We use a 95% confidence interval and the bootstrapping method to implement the mediation strategy described by (Preacher & Hayes, 2004). Table 6 demonstrates that the indirect effect is statistically significant (95 percent confidence interval > 0). An individual's propensity for making snap purchasing decisions modulates the effects of celebrity endorsement and peer influence. Table 6 demonstrates that the indirect effect of impulsiveness on correlations between predictors (celebrity endorsement and peer influence) and (impulsive buying behavior) is strong at a bootstrap confidence range of 95% (excluding 0%). This result indicates that materialism moderates the impact of the factors (celebrity endorsement and peer pressure) on irrational and compulsive buying. Bootstrapped results are displayed in Table 6.

The researchers used interaction terms to test hypotheses H9 and H10, which aimed to determine whether or not social media use moderated the link between celebrity endorsement and impulsiveness. As can be seen in Table 4, Figure 4, and Graph 1, the study found that social media use significantly and favourably moderated the link between celebrity endorsement and impulsiveness. There was statistical evidence that the interaction term served as a moderator of the association ($b = 0.126$, $p = 0.05$). It has also been shown that social media use mediates the link between being influenced by one's peers and being impulsive. As can be seen in Figure 5, Table 5, and Graph 5, the interaction term ($b = 0.082$, $p = 0.05$) acts as a statistically significant moderator.

Table: 4

		Estimate	P
ZImpulsiveness <---	ZCelebrity_Endorsement	.293	***
ZImpulsiveness <---	ZSocial_media_Use	.199	***
ZImpulsiveness <---	INT_CEN_SMU	.089	.032

Fig: 4

Figure 4.16 Social Media use as moderator between PIN and IMP

Table 3.1 Moderation Estimates

		Estimate	P
ZImpulsiveness <---	ZPeer_Influence	.320	***
ZImpulsiveness <---	ZSocial_media_Use	.202	***
ZImpulsiveness <---	INT_PIN_SMU	.095	.017

Graph 4.4 Social Media use Moderator between PIN and IMP

4. Discussion

The goal of this research was to find out if or not impulsive purchasing behaviour is related to social influence (celebrity endorsement and peer influence). The article also looked into how impulsiveness influenced the connections between people. In addition, the role that The SOR (Stimulus Organism Response) model, developed by Russell and Mehrabian (1977), examines the mediating role that social media plays in the interactions of young people which goes as follows: "different elements of the environment serve as stimuli (S), which in turn affect individuals' internal states (O), which in turn serve as organisms (O) that drive behavioural responses (R)." According to the findings of this research, impulsive purchasing behaviour is the behavioural consequence, with celebrity endorsement, peer influence, and social media use serving as the environmental Stimulus (S) components. Every single one of the assumptions is accepted. Media superstars and peers have a significant impact on today's youth. When making purchases, they look to media stars as role models. Similarly, the role of a peer can have profound effects. A trait of personality known as "impulsiveness" is the tendency to make hasty purchases. Personality development depends on a trifecta including both celebrity endorsement and peer influence. This is where today's youth find their motivation. This study's findings show that impulse purchases are significantly affected by both celebrity endorsement and social influence. The relationship between communication with peers and with famous people was found to have a beneficial effect on the propensity to make spontaneous purchases. There's an implication that, through social interaction, people become more prone to acting on impulse. These findings agree with those of prior studies. A positive correlation between stimuli (in this case, communication with peers and celebrities) and response (in this case, impulsive purchasing) was found. It suggests that impulsivity develops as a result of communicating with peers and celebrities, in line with findings from (Lueg et al., 2006) that Consumers' shopping attitudes and choices are profoundly influenced by word-of-mouth among their peers and their favourite celebrities (Shim, 1996) These findings corroborate earlier research (K. Chan & Prendergast, 2008; Z. C. Y. Chan et al., 2013; Z. N. Chen & Chia, 2006; La Ferle & Chan, 2008; M. S. W. Lee & Ahn, 2016; Mueller et al., 2011; Nga et

al., 2011). Relationships are mediated by impulsiveness. The findings are consistent with (Badgaiyan & Verma, 2014; S. B. G. Eysenck et al., 1985; McCrae & Costa Jr, 2008; Verplanken & Herabadi, 2001). Millennials and Gen Xers are more likely to use social networks than their parents' generation. The former is more common because of many variables. Our survey found that only 10% of students utilise portable electronic devices like laptops and smartphones. The government of Pakistan has made laptop computers and public Wi-Fi available at no cost to college students. The widespread availability of smart phones among young people, which provides them access to numerous media and social networking apps, also had a role in this development. It simplified access for young adults to videos on social media featuring celebrity endorsements of products. Finally, young adults have a plethora of friends and media figures with whom they identify and who share their interests. Young adults, in order to keep up appearances in their social circles, conform to the norms of the group when it comes to talking about money and material possessions. In particular, among young people, social media serves as a moderator between the social influence elements of celebrity endorsement and peer influences, and impulsiveness. All of the predictions hold true, indicating that social media does have an effect on a personality trait (impulsiveness) in certain people. These results agree with those found in (Fan & Gordon, 2014; Joshi & Rahman, 2019)

Theoretical contribution

Our findings expanded the existing body of knowledge. First, we put to the test and verified a theoretical framework that may be used to foretell characteristics of young people's personalities. All of the testable hypotheses in the underlying conceptual model were confirmed by the data. Our findings lend credence to various proposed explanations in the literature on the origins of impulsive behaviour. Therefore, this study is the first of its kind to systematically examine the connections between social and marketing factors, impulsive buying behaviour, and impulsiveness among young adults in Pakistan and, to a lesser extent, other countries where Islam is the dominant religion. Second, this research supports previously identified characteristics by showing that the development of compulsive purchasing is most strongly associated with sociological determinants in contemporary Islamic culture (K. Chan & Prendergast, 2008; K. Chan & Zhang, 2007), and, where impulsiveness acts as a mediator between other variables. This is due to the limited body of research showing impulsivity to be a mediator between environmental factors and compulsive purchasing. As a result, the present research added to our knowledge of the factors that influence compulsive buying. Implications. The results of this study provide important new information for policymakers about how to foster positive development of adolescent character qualities. As a result of these results, government policymakers can see that young adults in Policymakers may want to investigate the cause and effect of this trend. This essay implies that this is a worldwide issue; if this is the case, we need to look into solutions that have proven effective in nations with quite different demographics. Governments should promote education that helps young individuals form good shopping habits so that they can avoid becoming overly materialistic. Second, authorities should enact rules to lessen the impact of television advertising on obsessive behaviour and material accumulation because of the evidence linking the two. Instilling basic values in young children requires parents to spend quality time with them. They need to discourage children from gauging their consumption patterns against those of their friends.

5. Limitations and future research

Our study has some caveats that need to be taken into consideration. We started by collecting data from the respondents, who were all college students. Conclusions drawn from this study have limited external validity since the model's outputs may vary depending

on the context; findings may differ if the study were conducted with a different target audience in mind. Researchers in the future should test and reevaluate the conceptual model under new conditions. Second, the data was gathered from college students in the region of Punjab in Pakistan, where young people are more susceptible to the impact of peer groups and celebrity endorsements than in other parts of the country. To get a fuller picture of how young adults feel about the study components and about constructs in general, future studies should use larger samples and collect data from all universities in the province. Third, our research relied on a cross-sectional design. A longitudinal study could shed light on the concept of compulsive buying, which evolves over time and is not a unidimensional construct. Lastly, future studies should account for product type as a potential predictor and determinant of materialism and impulsive purchases. The influence of intergenerational dialogue on consumer behaviour could be the subject of future study.

6. Acknowledgment/Funding

This work was supported by the Deanship of Scientific Research, Vice Presidency for Graduate Studies and Scientific Research, King Faisal University, Saudi Arabia [Grant No. 5475]

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